

Research

Locus of control and Job satisfaction among Factory Employees in Multan, Pakistan

Sundas Irshad¹, Hafiz Muhammad Ihsan Zafeer^{2*}, Samra Maqbool², Samina Zamir², Uzma Sarwar², Sufyan Maqbool³

¹ School of Psychology, Bahauddin zakariya university Multan Pakistan

² School of Education- Shaanxi Normal University, Xi'an 710062, P.R. China

³ Bahauddin Zakriya University, Multan, Punjab Pakistan

***Corresponding author**

Email: hafizihsan28@gmail.com

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Abstract: The present study was aimed to discover the relationship between Locus of control on job satisfaction among factory employees regarding the different level of age and income. The sample size consisted of 300 employees working in one of the factories, which were situated in Multan, Punjab, Pakistan. The age ranges were from 17-50 years, whereas the income ranges were 5000-40000. Moreover, the hypothesis was also established to check the affiliation between Locus of control and job satisfaction. The quantitative survey method was used based on questionnaires, which had consisted of 48 items that highpoint the causes to adjust the Locus of control and job satisfaction level of the workers. The descriptive and One-Way ANOVA analysis were used as statistical techniques through SPSS for analysis. The results specified that employees with high Locus of control show high job satisfaction. Findings also suggested that different age groups indicate a different level of Locus of control and job satisfaction.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Locus of Control, Performance of Employees

1. Introduction

Job satisfaction of employees in the work environment is one of the significant goals of human resource administrators and professionals for better perfection and profitability. The Satisfaction of a job is a mental condition of the human psyche, and it is emotional to personal experience and desire; character frequently assumes an influential role. Practically all people consistently make progress toward Satisfaction in each part of life. But in an organizational setting, this might be identified with endeavoring towards making sure about a great job, with

decent compensation and high Satisfaction of job. Satisfaction with work has consistently been a significant aspect for professionals, human assets, directors, and academicians. In light of the explanation that Satisfaction of job essentially influences chief organizational results, for example, job involvement, the performance of individual, hierarchical efficiency, employee commitment, and employee absenteeism as well as employee turnover.

"Locus of control" is the term in psychology that states an individual's faith about what reasons the fortunate or unfortunate outcomes throughout his life, either all in all or a particular region like; academics or health. It also states to a person's generalized desire about where control over ensuing occasions dwells. As it were, who for sure is answerable for what occurs. It was begun (LOC) by Julian Rotter, in the year (1950) and characterized into two significant classifications, for instance, Internal and External. "Interior control" is that term which used to elaborate the faith that control of upcoming results lives practically in oneself (Ng, Sorensen, & Eby, 2006). Then again, "External control" suggests the hope that control is exterior of oneself, either in possession of other influential individuals or because of destiny or potential possibility (James & Wright, 1993). It tends to be said that individuals who build up an internal (LOC) accept they are liable for their prosperity. Those with external (LOC) take that destiny, luck, or external impacts decide their fortune (Gershaw, 1989).

Researchers elaborated that the kind of Locus of Control the individual brings influences the level of job satisfaction (Chen & Silverthorne, 2008). Job satisfaction has been characterized as a pleasurable passionate state because of examining a particular job, emotional response to the specific position, and a mentality towards career (Loher, Noe, Moeller, & Fitzgerald, 1985). It has contended that work fulfillment is a demeanor; however; points out that scholar ought to recognize the objects of cognitive assessment which influence (feeling, emotions), behaviors, and faiths. Maslow's theory describes that individuals pursue moving definite five needs in life like; psychological, social, safety, self-esteem, and self-actualization (Rani & Mariappan, 2011). In this paper was aimed to discover the association between Locus of control and job satisfaction among factory employees in Multan Pakistan, to explore this association, various factors had taken into consideration: Occupation, payment, support, conditional prizes, benefits, working actions, co-workers.

2. Literature Review

Locus of Control (LOC) in the working environment separates employees who accept they can practice command over their work and their condition through their personal activities employees who are pretty much independent. The distinctive contrast regarding the faith of individual control among internal and external will influence perfection levels. Research bolstered the immediate effect of LOC on the behaviors of individuals that affect job perfection and work Satisfaction in the working place (Judge & Bono, 2001). Essentially, another investigation recommended that people with inner LOC ought to be more satisfied with their job because they are more averse to remaining in a disappointing position and are bound to be fruitful in an association (Coleman, Irving, & Cooper, 1999). Perceiving that Satisfaction of job is prescient of employee turnover, it should not shock anyone that internals makes a move and would be required to search for different chances (either inside or with another organization) if in a disappointing job. On the other hand, facades tend not to make a move, and in this manner, regardless of whether they are disappointed they may remain at work until ecological components compel them to leave.

The studies of job satisfaction are essential for organizational conduct. According to Mullins (1999) job satisfaction is an inside state, an attitude. He also elaborates; job satisfaction can be related to individual sentiments of accomplishment, either impliedly or expressively. Scholars also defined that there are three commonly accepted dimensions for job satisfaction (Luthans, 2002).

Firstly, job satisfaction is a sensitive reaction to a work condition that can't see. It must be derived. Secondly, job satisfaction is habitually measured in what way adequate results happen or surpasses desires. For instance, if company affiliates give the impression like they are working much harder than others members in an organization, still, are accepting less remuneration, they will have a negative disposition toward their work, the authority, and collaborators. On the off chance that they trust they are being dealt well overall and are pay equally, they are possibly starting to have an inspirational mentality toward the work/job. Thirdly, job satisfaction denotes numerous attitudes regarding the most significant attributes of a job: work, occupation, promotion chances, salaries, support, conditional prizes, co-worker, and supervision.

The scholar displays that male culinary expressions workers had a different internal locus of control than female culinary expressions laborers. Inner Locus of Control was all together and

decidedly related to worker job satisfaction (Hsul, 2006). It is also reported that to forestall job disappointment and hold workers, bosses need to stay aware of changing qualities related to work. It is imperative to remain on top of the current worker esteems (Nerison, 1999). In the view of Murray (1999), he argued that increasing salaries and promotions is an impressive factor for individuals, increasing the job satisfaction level indirectly. Further argued, teamwork increases the job satisfaction level. In comparison, collaboration has also got a negative correlation along with assistance packages and correlated positively with overall job satisfaction (Kuye & Sulaimon, 2011).

Numerous studies indicate a positive and negative effect between Locus of control and job satisfaction regarding workers at the workplace in different organizational sectors—a survey conducted in 2006 in South Africa at a call center. The sample was consisted of 187 participants, with 34.76% (Male) and 65.24% (Female). Quantitative techniques were used to find out the relation between Locus of control and job satisfaction. The research findings show that the relationship positively correlated (Basson, Coetzee, & Carrim, 2006). Another study was conducted in 2011 in a Nigerian hospital. Five hundred twelve (512) participants were taken part in this study, and the same quantitative techniques were used. The study findings show that relationship positively correlated between Locus of control and job satisfaction (Igbeneghu & Popoola, 2011).

As per indicated by Kulcarni (1983) the United States of America (USA) to compare work satisfaction and Rotter's Internal-External Locus of Control. Two hundred (200) employees were taken from the banking and insurance company sectors. The findings showed significant negative relationships among external Locus of control and job satisfaction, whereas internal Locus of control stated a higher level of job satisfaction (Kulcarni, 1983). Similarly, in 2013 research conducted in India at the manufacturing sector between 60 participants with quantitative techniques to find the relationship between Locus of control and job satisfaction. The finding of this research was that the ties negatively correlated (Dhole & JaiminiT, 2013).

Figure 1: Conceptual theme of the study

3. Objective of the study

To discover the influence of work, Locus of control on job satisfaction among factory employees regarding age and income group in Multan, Pakistan.

4. Method and Material

The quantitative survey method was used in this study for initiating the data collection about work, Locus of control, job satisfaction (Latham, 2012). The scales were developed and translated into the local language for the ease of the participants. And the scale had consisted of 48 items.

4.1. Sample

The population was contained in the factory employees. The sample consisted of three hundred (300) factory workers employed at one of the factories situated in Multan, Punjab, Pakistan. The age range of participants was 17 to 50 years, and the income/salary ranges of participants were five thousand (5000) to forty thousand (40000).

4.2. Procedure

After getting permission from the factory's administration, the participants were approached individually. It had been told to the participants that the purpose of the study was to collect the information regarding the locus of control on job satisfaction. There were also said to them that data shall be kept off the record and shall only be used for this study. Then two closed questionnaires were administered among 300 employees, and 287 were got back. The data were collected on the five Likert scale ranges; 1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree.

4.3. Hypothesis of this study

H₁ Different age groups of employees will have a different level of job satisfaction.

H₂ Different income groups of employees will have a different level of job satisfaction.

H₃ Different age groups of employees will have a different factor of Locus of control.

H₄ Different income groups of employees will have a different factor of Locus of control.

5. Results and Analysis

Table 1: Demographic variable (Age Groups)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Age</i>		
Less than 20	82	28.2
21- 30	63	21.9
31- 40	73	25.5
Above 41	69	24.0
Total	287	100.0

Table 1 shows the Frequency and Percentage of the age of participants. There are 4 groups and have different level of age; less than 20 years (*f* 82, *p* 28.2%) 21-30 (*f* 63, *p* 21.9%), 31- 40 (*f* 73, *p* 25.5%), and Above 41 (*f* 69, *p* 24.0%).

Table 2: Demographic variable (Income Groups)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Income</i>		
5000-15000	77	26.5
16000-25000	69	24.0
26000-35000	55	19.1
Above 36000	88	30.0
Total	287	100.0

Table 2 shows the Frequency and Percentage of the income groups of participants. There are 4 groups and have got different package of incomes; 5000-15000 (*f* 77, *p* 26.5%) 16000-25000 (*f* 69, *p* 24.0%), 26000-35000 (*f* 55, *p* 19.1%), and Above 41 (*f* 88, *p* 30.0%).

Table 3: Age and Income-Based difference between groups of employees on the level of job satisfaction

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Std.Error</i>
<i>Age</i>				
Less than 20	82	42.1	5.03	1.129
21-30	63	42.9	4.85	.701
31-40	73	45.5	4.16	.717

Above 41	69	43.4	3.00	1.505
Total	287	43.32	4.639	.464
<i>Income</i>				
5000-15000	77	41.0	4.46	1.044
16000-25000	69	42.7	5.14	.856
26000-35000	55	43.6	3.23	.545
Above 36000	88	40.3	7.57	2.798
Total	287	43.3	4.66	.466

N = number of participants in a group; m = mean of the participant in a group; SD = standard deviation

Table 3 indicates the level of job satisfaction of employees in different age groups. The results reveal that the employees 31-40 years old have a high level of job satisfaction with the highest means of (45.5), and the lowest job satisfaction has shown in the group of employees less than 20 years with the mean of (42.1). Whereas the level of job satisfaction of employees in different income groups. The results show that the employees who come in 3rd group with the income (26000-35000) years old have a high level of job satisfaction with the highest means of (43.6), whereas the lowest job satisfaction of employees who come in the 1st group with an income (5000-15000) with the mean of (41.0).

Table 4: Age and Income-Based difference between groups of employees on the factor of locus of control

Variables	N	M	SD	Std.Error
<i>Age</i>				
Less than 20	82	19.2	4.58	1.019
21-30	63	20.4	3.52	.515
31-40	73	20.6	3.36	.629
Above 41	69	20.5	5.56	2.784
Total	287	20.2	3.76	.367
<i>Income</i>				
5000-15000	77	20.9	4.10	.966
16000-25000	69	19.9	3.47	.569
26000-35000	55	20.2	3.77	.545
Above 36000	88	20.4	7.97	1.435
Total	287	20.3	3.76	.355

N = number of participants in a group; m = mean of the participant in a group; SD = standard deviation

Table 4 depicts the different factors of Locus of control in various age and income groups of employees. Mean identify the factors of Locus of Control present in the employees. The employees (31-40) years old have the highest mean of (20.6), and the lowest mean (19.2)

analyzed in less than a 20-year-old group. While from income groups with (5000-15000) have the highest mean of (20.9), and the lowest mean (19.9) found with the (16000-25000) income.

Table 5: One-Way ANOVA showing the level of job satisfaction between Age and Income groups

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Sum of Sq.</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Sq.</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Age</i>					
Between group	53.26	3	17.77	4.68	.815
Within group	2074.16	96	21.60		
Total	2126.36	99			
<i>Income</i>					
Between group	112.51	3	37.31	1.788	.153
Within group	2015.16	96	20.99		
Total	2127.75	99			

Table 5 specifies the level of job satisfaction between age and income groups. Age; if we presume the significant value as (0.90), then the results clearly show no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction between different age groups because the significant value is (.815), which is high than (0.10). In contrast, in income groups, there is also a non-significant difference in job satisfaction, because the significant value is (.153), which is high than (0.10).

Table 6: One-Way ANOVA showing the relationship of factor of Locus of control between age and income groups

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Sum of Sq.</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Sq.</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Age</i>					
Between group	26.61	3	8.69	.615	.605
Within group	1365.55	96	14.27		
Total	1387.16	99			
<i>Income</i>					
Between group	14.41	3	4.31	.335	.805
Within group	1383.75	96	14.41		
Total	1397.16	99			

Table 6 lay down the factor of Locus of control between different age and income groups. If we presume the significant value as (0.90), then the results clearly show that there is a non-significant difference in the factor of Locus of control between different age groups because the significant value is (.605), which is higher than (0.10). In income groups, the results clearly show that there is no significant difference in the factor of Locus of control between different income groups because the significant value is .805, which is bigger than (0.10).

6. Conclusion

In any association, work execution is generally founded on worker work satisfaction. A gratified individual may perform better in the working environment and home than to an individual with disappointment. It is essential to discover the relationship between locus of control and representatives working in various hierarchical segments. In the wake of examining and investigating the quantities of exploration concentrates in the current article, it is revealed that personalities who have an inner locus of control are cheerier with their status what they have than to characters that have no locus of control. The innovations of this research relate to various investigations that show persons that have an inner locus of control are happier, beneficial and most work arranged as compared to their colleagues who have no locus of control.

The results portray that the locus of control is a prominent variable in considering the work satisfaction of the employees in various public and private sectors. Previously researches have been conducted in this field that designates the understanding of the mediate position of locus of control in job satisfaction among workers (April, Dharani, & Peters, 2012; Wang, Bowling, & Eschleman, 2010), (Singh & Kumar6Dubey, 2011). In contrast, the researchers have verified that a person is more conducive to job satisfaction having an internal locus of control as compared to the external locus. In this manner, during the hour of screening, planning in any imposing part, the experiment of locus of control should be proposed mainly to executive positions in any (public & private) sector.

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Conflicts of Interest

We, the authors, declared no conflicts of interest in this study.

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